

Supplementary material for “A consistent finite-strain thermomechanical quasi-nonlinear-viscoelastic viscoplastic constitutive model for thermoplastic polymers”

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Note: This document contains the partial derivatives for the elastoplastic integration algorithm and algorithmic tangent operators of the constitutive model presented in the article, "A consistent finite-strain thermomechanical quasi-nonlinear-viscoelastic viscoplastic constitutive model for thermoplastic polymers".

Appendix E. Partial Derivatives for the Elasto-Plastic Integration Scheme

First, the derivatives of the scalar A , defined in Eq. (B.25), used in the derivatives of $G(\Gamma, \Delta\gamma)$ are stated explicitly:

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial \Delta\gamma} = \frac{1}{2A} \left(12\phi_e \frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial \Delta\gamma} + \frac{8}{3}\beta^2 \phi_p \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial A}{\partial \Gamma} = \frac{1}{2A} \left(12\phi_e \frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial \Gamma} + \frac{8}{3}\beta^2 \phi_p \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \Gamma} \right). \quad (\text{E.1})$$

Second, using Eqs. (82), the hardening moduli derivatives are needed in the derivatives of $\bar{F}(\Gamma, \Delta\gamma)$:

$$H_2 = \frac{\partial a_2}{\partial \Delta\gamma} = -\frac{\alpha}{\sigma_c^{\alpha+1}} H_c a_{T_\gamma}^c, \quad (\text{E.2})$$

$$H_1 = \frac{\partial a_1}{\partial \Delta\gamma} = \frac{3}{\sigma_c} \left[\frac{\alpha m^{\alpha-1}}{m+1} - \frac{m^\alpha - 1}{(m+1)^2} \right] \frac{(H_t \sigma_c a_{T_\gamma}^t - H_c \sigma_t a_{T_\gamma}^c)}{\sigma_c^2} - 3 \frac{m^\alpha - 1}{m+1} \frac{H_c a_{T_\gamma}^c}{\sigma_c^2}, \quad (\text{E.3})$$

$$H_0 = \frac{\partial a_0}{\partial \Delta\gamma} = \frac{(\alpha m^{\alpha-1} + 1)(m+1) - m^\alpha - m}{(m+1)^2} \frac{(H_t \sigma_c a_{T_\gamma}^t - H_c \sigma_t a_{T_\gamma}^c)}{\sigma_c^2}. \quad (\text{E.4})$$

where, $H_{t|c}$ are hardening moduli-like functions of γ obtained as the 1st order derivatives of yield stresses $\sigma_{t|c}$ defined in Eqs. (86). Third, within ϕ_e and ϕ_p , there exists \mathbf{B} and its

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derivatives with respect to the unknowns. Referring to Eqs. (B.18) , the following is written:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} = \frac{k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial(\Gamma \mathbf{Q})}{\partial \Delta\gamma} + \frac{k^2 \Gamma \mathbf{Q}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} - \frac{k^2 \Gamma \mathbf{Q} H_{\mathbf{B}} + \mathbf{B}^{n*}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} + \frac{3}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{B}^{n*}}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{Q}} : \frac{\partial \text{dev } \phi}{\partial \Delta\gamma}, \quad (\text{E.5})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial \Gamma} = \frac{k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial(\Gamma \mathbf{Q})}{\partial \Gamma} + \frac{3}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{B}^{n*}}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{Q}} : \frac{\partial \text{dev } \phi}{\partial \Gamma}, \quad (\text{E.6})$$

where $C_{\mathbf{B}}$ is independent of Γ and its derivative with respect to $\Delta\gamma$ reads, following Eq. (B.19):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} &= -\frac{m_{\gamma c}}{H_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \gamma} - m_{\gamma c} \Delta\gamma \left(-\frac{1}{H_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \left(\frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \gamma} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{H_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \gamma^2} \right) + \dots \\ &\dots - \Delta T \left(-\frac{1}{H_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \gamma} \frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} + \frac{1}{H_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \gamma \partial T} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.7})$$

Fourth, acknowledging that $\phi = \text{dev } \phi + \phi_p \mathbf{I}$ and the definitions of the invariants stated in Eqs. (73) , the following expected primitive derivatives are noted:

$$\frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial \text{dev } \phi} = \frac{3 \text{dev } \phi}{2 \phi_e}, \quad (\text{E.8})$$

$$\frac{\partial \text{dev } \phi}{\partial(\cdot)} = \frac{\partial \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial(\cdot)} - \frac{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{B}}{\partial(\cdot)}, \quad (\text{E.9})$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial(\cdot)} = \frac{\partial \hat{p}_e}{\partial(\cdot)} - \frac{1}{3} \frac{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{B}}{\partial(\cdot)}, \quad (\text{E.10})$$

where (\cdot) refers to either $\Delta\gamma$ or Γ and \hat{p}_e is the pressure part of $\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e$ defined in Eq. (59). Fifth, the derivatives of $\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e$ are expressed in terms of \mathbf{E}_e , which is expressed in terms of the corrector tensor $(\Gamma \mathbf{Q})$ as observed in Eq. (B.16), as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{p}_e}{\partial(\cdot)} = \frac{\partial \hat{p}_e}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} \frac{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e}{\partial(\Gamma \text{tr } \mathbf{Q})} \frac{\partial(\Gamma \text{tr } \mathbf{Q})}{\partial(\cdot)} = -\frac{\partial \hat{p}_e}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} \frac{\partial(\Gamma \text{tr } \mathbf{Q})}{\partial(\cdot)}, \quad (\text{E.11})$$

$$\frac{\partial \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial(\cdot)} = \frac{\partial \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_e}{\partial(\Gamma \mathbf{Q})} : \frac{\partial(\Gamma \mathbf{Q})}{\partial(\cdot)} = -\frac{\partial \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} : \frac{\partial(\Gamma \mathbf{Q})}{\partial(\cdot)}, \quad (\text{E.12})$$

where the terms $\frac{\partial \hat{p}_e}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e}$ and $\frac{\partial \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e}$ stem from the constitutive matrix and are both evaluated in Appendix F.3. Last, the derivatives of the corrector tensor, $\Gamma \mathbf{Q}$, with respect to the unknowns through the definition of the flow normal in Eq. (B.9) are required:

$$\frac{\partial(\Gamma \mathbf{Q})}{\partial \Delta\gamma} = \Gamma \left(3 \frac{\partial \text{dev } \phi}{\partial \Delta\gamma} + \frac{2\beta}{3} \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \mathbf{I} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial(\Gamma \mathbf{Q})}{\partial \Gamma} = \mathbf{Q} + \Gamma \left(3 \frac{\partial \text{dev } \phi}{\partial \Gamma} + \frac{2\beta}{3} \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \Gamma} \mathbf{I} \right). \quad (\text{E.13})$$

Therefore, it is clear that the derivatives of ϕ_e and ϕ_p with respect to the unknowns $\Delta\gamma$ and Γ are implicit.

Using the above relations the derivatives of ϕ_p are obtained. $\frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \Delta\gamma}$ is stated below using Eq. (E.10), rearranging and writing in terms of $\frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial(\cdot)}$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \Delta\gamma} &= \left(1 + 2\beta \Gamma \left(\frac{\partial \hat{p}_e}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} + \frac{k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{3 C_{\mathbf{B}}} \right) \right)^{-1} \\ &\quad \left(\frac{2\beta k^2 \Gamma \phi_p}{3} \left(\frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} - \frac{1}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \right) + \frac{1}{3} \frac{\text{tr } \mathbf{B}^n}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.14})$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \Gamma} = \left(1 + 2\beta \Gamma \left(\frac{\partial \hat{p}_e}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} + \frac{k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{3 C_{\mathbf{B}}} \right) \right)^{-1} (-2\beta \phi_p) \left(\frac{\partial \hat{p}_e}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} + \frac{k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{3 C_{\mathbf{B}}} \right). \quad (\text{E.15})$$

Note that, in both the cases of $\frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \Delta \gamma}$ and $\frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \Gamma}$, the term to be inverted remains the same. This is a consequence of the flow normal definition and is expected to repeat in case of the derivatives of $\text{dev } \phi$ as given below:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \text{dev } \phi}{\partial \Delta \gamma} &= \left(\mathcal{I} + 3\Gamma \left(\frac{\partial \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} \otimes \mathbf{I} + \frac{\partial \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e} : \mathcal{I}^{dev} \right) : \mathcal{I} \dots \right. \\ &\quad \left. \dots + \frac{3\Gamma k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} : \mathcal{I} + \frac{3}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{B}^{n*}}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{Q}} \frac{\partial \text{dev } \phi}{\partial \Delta \gamma} \right)^{-1} : \mathcal{D}_{\gamma}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.16})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \text{dev } \phi}{\partial \Gamma} &= \left(\mathcal{I} + 3\Gamma \left(\frac{\partial \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} \otimes \mathbf{I} + \frac{\partial \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e} : \mathcal{I}^{dev} \right) : \mathcal{I} \dots \right. \\ &\quad \left. \dots + \frac{3\Gamma k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} : \mathcal{I} + \frac{3}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{B}^{n*}}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{Q}} : \mathcal{I} \right)^{-1} : \mathcal{D}_{\Gamma}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.17})$$

where the terms on the RHS are:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{\gamma} &= \left(\left(-\frac{\partial \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} \otimes \mathbf{I} - \frac{\partial \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e} : \mathcal{I}^{dev} \right) : \frac{2\beta\Gamma}{3} \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \Delta \gamma} \mathbf{I} \right) \dots \\ &\quad \dots + 3k^2 \Gamma \text{dev } \phi \left(\frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta \gamma} - \frac{1}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta \gamma} \right) + \frac{\text{dev } \mathbf{B}^{n*}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta \gamma}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.18})$$

$$\mathcal{D}_{\Gamma} = \left(-\frac{\partial \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} \otimes \mathbf{I} - \frac{\partial \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e} : \mathcal{I}^{dev} \right) : \left(\mathbf{Q} + \frac{2\beta\Gamma}{3} \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \Gamma} \mathbf{I} \right) - \frac{3k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \text{dev } \phi. \quad (\text{E.19})$$

where the term $\frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \Gamma}$ comes from the solution of Eq. (E.15).

Appendix F. Partial Derivatives of Thermoviscoelasticity

Appendix F.1. Partial Derivatives in TTSP

The derivatives of the shifted time-steps with respect to the temperature read:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial T} \left(\Delta t^{\#} \Big|_{\text{mid|rec}} \right) = \frac{\Delta t}{c_{\text{mid|rec}}} \sum_{k=1}^P W_k \frac{\partial}{\partial T(\epsilon(x_k))} \left[\frac{1}{a_T(T(\epsilon(x_k)))} \right] \frac{dT(\epsilon(x_k))}{dT}. \quad (\text{F.1})$$

Using a linear interpolation for the temperatures at Gauss points leads to:

$$T(\epsilon(x_k)) = \frac{1}{\Delta t} [t^{n+1} - \epsilon(x_k)] T(t^n) + \frac{1}{\Delta t} [\epsilon(x_k) - t^n] T, \quad \text{and} \quad (\text{F.2})$$

$$\frac{dT(\epsilon(x_k))}{dT} = \frac{1}{\Delta t} [\epsilon(x_k) - t^n]. \quad (\text{F.3})$$

Lastly, the derivative of the shift factor in Eq. (48) with respect to the temperature is given by:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial T} \left[\frac{1}{a_T(T)} \right] = \frac{1}{a_T(T)} \left[\frac{C_1 C_2}{(C_2 + T - T_{\text{ref}})^2} \right]. \quad (\text{F.4})$$

Appendix F.2. Partial Derivatives of the Rotation Matrix

The derivatives of the rotated tensor in superscript * are evaluated in terms of the partial derivatives of the eigenvalues and bases, given as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_e^{n*}}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} = \sum_{k=1}^3 \omega_k^n \frac{\partial (\mathbf{N}_k \otimes \mathbf{N}_k)}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e}. \quad (\text{F.5})$$

To differentiate the bases, the following formulation is used:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial (\mathbf{N}_k \otimes \mathbf{N}_k)}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} &= \frac{1}{\omega_k} \mathbf{N}_k \otimes \mathbf{N}_k \otimes \frac{\partial \omega_k}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} \dots \\
&\dots + \frac{\omega_k}{z_k} \left(\mathcal{I} - \mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{I} \otimes \frac{\partial \omega_k}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} + \det \mathbf{E}_e \left(\frac{1}{\omega_k} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_e^{-1}}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} - \frac{1}{\omega_k^2} \mathbf{E}_e^{-1} \otimes \frac{\partial \omega_k}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} \right) \right) \dots \\
&\dots + \frac{\omega_k}{z_k} \left(\frac{\det \mathbf{E}_e}{\omega_k} \mathbf{E}_e^{-1} \otimes \mathbf{E}_e^{-1} \right) \dots \\
&\dots - \frac{1}{z_k} \mathbf{N}_k \otimes \mathbf{N}_k \otimes \frac{\partial z_k}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e}, \tag{F.6}
\end{aligned}$$

where ω_k is the k^{th} eigenvalue, \mathbf{N}_k is the k^{th} eigenvector, $z_k = 2\omega_k^2 - \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e \omega_k + \frac{\det \mathbf{E}_e}{\omega_k}$ and the remaining derivatives are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \omega_k}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} &= \mathbf{N}_k \otimes \mathbf{N}_k, \\
\frac{\partial z_k}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} &= 4\omega_k \frac{\partial \omega_k}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} - \omega_k \mathbf{I} - \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e \frac{\partial \omega_k}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} + \frac{\det \mathbf{E}_e}{\omega_k} \mathbf{E}_e^{-1} - \frac{\det \mathbf{E}_e}{\omega_k^2} \frac{\partial \omega_k}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e}. \tag{F.7}
\end{aligned}$$

Appendix F.3. Partial Derivatives of the Co-rotational Kirchhoff Stress

The derivatives of $\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e$ are presented here using its definition in Eq. (59) and the branch stresses in Eqs. (45) and (46). Then, the constitutive tensor $\frac{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e}$ is as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} = \frac{\partial \hat{p}_e}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} \mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{I} + \frac{\partial \text{dev} \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} \otimes \mathbf{I} + \frac{\partial \text{dev} \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{E}_e} : \mathcal{I}^{dev}, \tag{F.8}$$

where, on the RHS, the first term is the equivalent of the effective bulk modulus, the second term is the dependence of the effective shear modulus on the volumetric strain introduced to account for elastic tension-compression asymmetry and the last term is the equivalent of the effective shear modulus. Each of those is elaborated on below:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{p}_e}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} = K_{\infty 0} \left(\frac{\partial A_{\infty}}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}} + A_{\infty} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^N K_{i0} \left(\frac{\partial A_i}{\partial \text{tr} \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i} \frac{\partial \text{tr} \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} \text{tr} \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i + A_i \right), \tag{F.9}$$

$$\frac{\partial \text{dev} \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} = 2G_{\infty 0} \left(\frac{\partial B_{\infty}}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} \text{dev} \mathbf{E}_e \right) + \sum_{i=1}^N 2G_{i0} \left(\frac{\partial B_i}{\partial \text{tr} \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i} \frac{\partial \text{tr} \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} \text{dev} \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i \right), \tag{F.10}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \text{dev} \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{E}_e} &= 2G_{\infty 0} \left(\text{dev} \mathbf{E}_e \otimes \frac{\partial B_{\infty}}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{E}_e} + B_{\infty} \mathcal{I} \right) \dots \\
&\dots + \sum_{i=1}^N 2G_{i0} \left(\text{dev} \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i \otimes \left(\frac{\partial B_i}{\partial \text{dev} \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i} : \frac{\partial \text{dev} \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{E}_e} \right) + B_i \frac{\partial \text{dev} \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{E}_e} \right), \tag{F.11}
\end{aligned}$$

where, using the solution to the convolutions integral for the volumetric terms in Eq. (49) and the deviatoric terms corrected for coaxiality in Eq. (55) leads to:

$$\frac{\partial \text{tr} \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} = \exp \left(- \frac{\Delta t^{\#} \Big|_{\text{mid}}}{k_i} \right), \tag{F.12}$$

$$\frac{\partial \text{dev} \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{E}_e} = \exp \left(- \frac{\Delta t^{\#} \Big|_{\text{rec}}}{g_i} \right) \frac{\partial \text{dev} \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i^{n^*}}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{E}_e} + \exp \left(- \frac{\Delta t^{\#} \Big|_{\text{mid}}}{g_i} \right) \left(\mathcal{I} - \frac{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{E}_e^{n^*}}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{E}_e} \right). \tag{F.13}$$

The rotated tensors in superscript $*$ are derived in terms of the partial derivatives of the eigenvalues and bases and noting that a similar correction for coaxiality is applied to the backstress, \mathbf{B} , in Appendix B.3 and Appendix B.4, yield:

$$\frac{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e^{n*}}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e} = \sum_{k=1}^3 \omega_k^n \frac{\partial (\mathbf{N}_k \otimes \mathbf{N}_k)}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e}, \quad \frac{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{B}^{n*}}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{Q}} = \sum_{k=1}^3 \omega_k^n \frac{\partial (\mathbf{M}_k \otimes \mathbf{M}_k)}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{Q}}. \quad (\text{F.14})$$

The Eq. (F.5) in Appendix F.2 is used for the above derivative.

The derivatives of the scalars, A_∞ and B_∞ in Eqs. (42), in terms of \mathbf{E}_e , noting that $\frac{\partial(\cdot)}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} = \frac{\partial(\cdot)}{\partial \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}}$, are as follows:

$$\frac{\partial A_\infty}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} = f_{\text{reg}} \frac{\partial A_{t_\infty}}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} + \frac{\partial f_{\text{reg}}}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} A_{t_\infty} + C_{0_\infty} \left((1 - f_{\text{reg}}) \frac{\partial A_{c_\infty}}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} - \frac{\partial f_{\text{reg}}}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} A_{c_\infty} \right), \quad (\text{F.15})$$

$$\frac{\partial B_\infty}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} = \frac{\partial f_{\text{reg}}}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} B_{t_\infty} - C_{0_\infty} \frac{\partial f_{\text{reg}}}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} B_{c_\infty}, \quad (\text{F.16})$$

$$\frac{\partial B_\infty}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e} = f_{\text{reg}} \frac{\partial B_{t_\infty}}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e} + C_{0_\infty} (1 - f_{\text{reg}}) \frac{\partial B_{c_\infty}}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e}, \quad (\text{F.17})$$

using

$$\frac{\partial A_{t_\infty}}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} = - \frac{V_{t_1} \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}}{(V_{t_1} \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}^2 + V_{t_2})^{\frac{3}{2}}} + 2V_{t_3} V_{t_5} \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}} \text{sech}^2(\text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}^2), \quad (\text{F.18})$$

$$\frac{\partial B_{t_\infty}}{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e} = \left(- \frac{D_{t_1}}{(D_{t_1} \|\text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e\|^2 + D_{t_2})^{\frac{3}{2}}} + 2D_{t_3} D_{t_5} \text{sech}^2(\|\text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e\|^2) \right) \text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e, \quad (\text{F.19})$$

$$\frac{\partial f_{\text{reg}}}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_e} = \frac{\xi \exp(-\xi \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}})}{(1 + \exp(-\xi \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}))^2}. \quad (\text{F.20})$$

Derivatives of A_{c_∞} and B_{c_∞} can be inferred from their tension counterparts above. Lastly, changing the arguments in the above relations from \mathbf{E}_{eff} to \mathfrak{E}_i gives the corresponding derivatives for A_i and B_i .

The co-rotational Kirchhoff stress also has a dependency on temperature through the WLF shift factor and thermal expansion which is evident in the Eqs. (38), (45), (46), (49), (50) and (59) in Section 3.2. Although preemptive, the corresponding partial derivatives with respect to temperature, dubbed here with the superscript $(\cdot)^{aT}$, are useful, such that the derivative $\frac{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e^{aT}}{\partial T}$ is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e^{aT}}{\partial T} &= \underbrace{\left(-K_{\infty 0} \left(\frac{\partial A_\infty}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}} \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}} + A_\infty \right) \left(3\alpha_\infty + 3 \frac{\partial \alpha_\infty}{\partial T} (T - T_0) \right) + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial p_i^{aT}}{\partial T} \right) \mathbf{I}}_{\frac{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e^{aT}}{\partial T}} \dots \\ &\dots + \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_i^{aT}}{\partial T}}_{\frac{\partial \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e^{aT}}{\partial T}}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{F.21})$$

where $\frac{\partial \widehat{p}_e^{aT}}{\partial T}$ is the thermal expansion term and the shift factor temperature dependence of the volumetric terms and $\frac{\partial \widehat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e^{aT}}{\partial T}$ is only the shift factor temperature dependence of the deviatoric terms. The Maxwell branch shift-factor temperature dependency is shown below:

$$\frac{\partial \widehat{p}_i^{aT}}{\partial T} = K_{i0} \left(A_i + \frac{\partial A_i}{\partial \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i} \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i \right) \frac{\partial \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial T}, \quad (\text{F.22})$$

$$\frac{\partial \text{dev } \widehat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_i^{aT}}{\partial T} = 2G_{i0} \left(B_i \frac{\partial \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial T} + \left(\frac{\partial B_i}{\partial \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i} \frac{\partial \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial T} + \frac{\partial B_i}{\partial \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i} : \frac{\partial \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial T} \right) \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i \right), \quad (\text{F.23})$$

where the shifted times from Eqs. (F.1) are explicitly seen in the Maxwell branch strain $\boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i$ derivatives:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial T} &= -\frac{1}{k_i} \exp \left(-\frac{\Delta t^\#|_{\text{rec}}}{k_i} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial T} \left(\Delta t^\#|_{\text{rec}} \right) \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i^n \dots \\ &\dots - \frac{1}{k_i} \exp \left(-\frac{\Delta t^\#|_{\text{mid}}}{k_i} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial T} \left(\Delta t^\#|_{\text{mid}} \right) (\text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}} - \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}^n) \dots \\ &\dots - \exp \left(-\frac{\Delta t^\#|_{\text{mid}}}{k_i} \right) \left(3\alpha_\infty + 3 \frac{\partial \alpha_\infty}{\partial T} (T - T_0) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{F.24})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial T} &= -\frac{1}{g_i} \exp \left(-\frac{\Delta t^\#|_{\text{rec}}}{g_i} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial T} \left(\Delta t^\#|_{\text{rec}} \right) \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i^{n*} \dots \\ &\dots - \frac{1}{g_i} \exp \left(-\frac{\Delta t^\#|_{\text{mid}}}{g_i} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial T} \left(\Delta t^\#|_{\text{mid}} \right) (\text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e - \text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e^{n*}). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{F.25})$$

Appendix G. Complete Effective Material Tangent Operators

The effective tangent operators for the 1st PK stress (\mathbf{P}), heat flux (\mathbf{Q}) and heat source (W_M) are presented here in full detail.

Appendix G.1. 1st PK Stress

From Eq. (88), the tangents of \mathbf{P} with respect to \mathbf{F} and T in a (pseudo-)damaged state are given below:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{P}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = \frac{\partial \widehat{\mathbf{P}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \zeta + \widehat{\mathbf{P}} \otimes \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{P}}{\partial T} = \frac{\partial \widehat{\mathbf{P}}}{\partial T} \zeta + \widehat{\mathbf{P}} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial T}, \quad (\text{G.1})$$

where the terms $\frac{\partial \widehat{\mathbf{P}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}}$ and $\frac{\partial \widehat{\mathbf{P}}}{\partial T}$ are the mechanical and thermal tangents of $\widehat{\mathbf{P}}$ in the undamaged state. Using Eq. (88), they are explicitly stated below:

$$\frac{\partial \widehat{\mathbf{P}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_e}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \cdot 2 \cdot (\widehat{\mathbf{S}}_e \cdot \mathbf{F}_p^{-T}) + \mathbf{F}_e \cdot 1 \cdot \frac{\partial \widehat{\mathbf{S}}_e}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \cdot 2 \cdot \mathbf{F}_p^{-T} + (\mathbf{F}_e \cdot \widehat{\mathbf{S}}_e) \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_p^{-T}}{\partial \mathbf{F}}, \quad (\text{G.2})$$

$$\frac{\partial \widehat{\mathbf{P}}}{\partial T} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_e}{\partial T} \cdot (\widehat{\mathbf{S}}_e \cdot \mathbf{F}_p^{-1}) + \mathbf{F}_e \cdot \frac{\partial \widehat{\mathbf{S}}_e}{\partial T} \cdot \mathbf{F}_p^{-1} + (\mathbf{F}_e \cdot \widehat{\mathbf{S}}_e) \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_p^{-1}}{\partial T}, \quad (\text{G.3})$$

where in the 1st equation, the superscripts (\cdot^i) and (\cdot^i) imply tensor dot product operations with the i^{th} index of the tensor on the left and tensor on the right, respectively. Then follow the derivatives of $\widehat{\mathbf{S}}_e$ using its relation with $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e$:

$$\frac{\partial \widehat{\mathbf{S}}_e}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = \frac{\partial \widehat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \cdot 1,2,1,2 \cdot \boldsymbol{\mathcal{L}}_e + \widehat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e \cdot 1,2 \cdot \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\mathcal{L}}_e}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \widehat{\mathbf{S}}_e}{\partial T} = \frac{\partial \widehat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial T} \cdot 1,2 \cdot \boldsymbol{\mathcal{L}}_e + \widehat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e \cdot 1,2 \cdot \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\mathcal{L}}_e}{\partial T}. \quad (\text{G.4})$$

The 4th order tensor $\mathcal{L}_e = \frac{\partial \ln \mathbf{C}_e}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e} = \mathcal{I}^{2,1} \mathbf{C}_e^{-1}$ and its derivative with \mathbf{C}_e , $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_e}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e} = \mathcal{I}^{2,1} \mathcal{I}^{2,1} \mathbf{C}_e^{-1}$. \mathbf{C}_e^{-1} , with \mathcal{I} being the 4th order symmetric identity tensor, stem from the definition of log strain \mathbf{E}_e . Then its requisite derivatives are as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_e}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_e}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e} \underset{5,6;1,2}{\cdot} \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_e}{\partial T} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_e}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e} \underset{5,6;1,2}{\cdot} \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e}{\partial T}. \quad (\text{G.5})$$

The derivatives of $\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e$ are expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = \frac{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_e}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial T} = \frac{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e^{aT}}{\partial T} + \frac{\partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_e}{\partial T}, \quad (\text{G.6})$$

where the elaboration in using $\frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}}$ is made for convenience and the remaining derivatives of $\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_e$ are derived in Appendix F.3. Moving on to the deformation measures, the derivatives of \mathbf{E}_e , using Eq. (B.16):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_e}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} &= \frac{1}{2} \mathcal{L}_e^{\text{pr}} - \underbrace{\left(\mathbf{Q} \otimes \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} + \Gamma \frac{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{Q}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} + \frac{\Gamma}{3} \mathbf{I} \otimes \frac{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{Q}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \right)}_{\frac{\partial(\Gamma \mathbf{Q})}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}}, \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_e}{\partial T} &= - \underbrace{\left(\mathbf{Q} \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial T} + \Gamma \frac{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{Q}}{\partial T} + \frac{\Gamma}{3} \frac{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{Q}}{\partial T} \mathbf{I} \right)}_{\frac{\partial(\Gamma \mathbf{Q})}{\partial T}}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.7})$$

where the negative terms are the derivatives of the corrector tensor $\Gamma \mathbf{Q}$. The 4th order tensor $\mathcal{L}_e^{\text{pr}} = \frac{\partial \ln \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}$ is constructed in the same way as \mathcal{L}_e . The conversion tensor $\frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}}$, used in Eq. (G.6), is given below:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = 2 \mathbf{F}_e^{\text{pr}T} \underset{1,3}{\otimes} \underset{2,4}{\otimes} \mathbf{F}_p^{n-1}. \quad (\text{G.8})$$

Note that the dyadic product, $(\cdot) \otimes (\cdot)$, for two 2nd order tensors conventionally follows the indices as $(\cdot) \underset{1,2}{\otimes} \underset{3,4}{\otimes} (\cdot)$, unless stated otherwise as was the case in the relationships above. Then, the derivatives of \mathbf{C}_e stem from its relation with \mathbf{F}_e , i.e., $\mathbf{C}_e = \mathbf{F}_e^T \cdot \mathbf{F}_e$:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = \mathbf{F}_e^T \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_e}{\partial \mathbf{F}} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_e^T}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \cdot \mathbf{F}_e \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e}{\partial T} = \mathbf{F}_e^T \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_e}{\partial T} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_e^T}{\partial T} \cdot \mathbf{F}_e, \quad (\text{G.9})$$

and using the following general relation for derivatives of the inverse of an arbitrary 2nd-order tensor, say \mathbf{C}_e , with respect to a tensor of an arbitrary order, say $\boldsymbol{\mathcal{Y}}$:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{-1}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\mathcal{Y}}} = - \mathbf{C}_e^{-1} \underset{1}{\cdot} \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\mathcal{Y}}} \underset{2}{\cdot} \mathbf{C}_e^{-1}. \quad (\text{G.10})$$

The derivatives of \mathbf{F}_e occurring in the above relations are easy to develop:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_e}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = \mathbf{I} \underset{1,3}{\otimes} \underset{4,2}{\otimes} \mathbf{F}_p^{-1} + \mathbf{F} \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_p^{-1}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_e}{\partial T} = \mathbf{F} \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_p^{-1}}{\partial T}. \quad (\text{G.11})$$

Before further elaboration, note that all the mechanical derivatives hereafter are performed with respect to \mathbf{C}_e^{pr} for convenience. Then, the derivatives of the plastic deformation gradient, \mathbf{F}_p , using Eq. (B.11) reads:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_p}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} = \left[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \left(\mathbf{Q} \otimes \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} + \Gamma \frac{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{Q}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} + \frac{\Gamma}{3} \mathbf{I} \otimes \frac{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{Q}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \right) \right] \cdot \mathbf{F}_p^n, \quad (\text{G.12})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_p}{\partial T} = \left[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \left(\mathbf{Q} \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial T} + \Gamma \frac{\partial \text{dev } \mathbf{Q}}{\partial T} + \frac{\Gamma}{3} \frac{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{Q}}{\partial T} \mathbf{I} \right) \right] \cdot \mathbf{F}_p^n. \quad (\text{G.13})$$

The derivatives of Γ are estimated using consistency conditions for yielding in the next subsection, Appendix G.2. Whereas, the recurring derivatives of \mathbf{Q} need to be evaluated through implicit relations in ϕ similar to the ones encountered previously in the Section Appendix B.2. The derivatives are written in the terms of the \mathbf{Q} and then inverted to obtain the derivatives of ϕ . This requires the derivatives of the backstress \mathbf{B} using the definition of backstress in Eqs. (B.18) and that of the flow normal in Eq. (B.9):

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} = \frac{1}{3} \mathbf{I} \otimes \frac{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{B}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} + \frac{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{B}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}, \quad (\text{G.14})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial T} = \frac{1}{3} \frac{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{B}}{\partial T} \mathbf{I} + \frac{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{B}}{\partial T}. \quad (\text{G.15})$$

Elaborating and splitting into volumetric and deviatoric parts, these relations lead to:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{B}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} &= 2\beta k^2 \left(\left(\frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \frac{1}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} - \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \right) \frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \Gamma \phi_p + \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \left(\frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \phi_p + \Gamma \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \right) \right) \dots \\ &\dots - \frac{\text{tr} \mathbf{B}^n}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.16})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{B}}{\partial T} &= 2\beta k^2 \left(\left(\frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} \frac{1}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} - \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} \right) \Gamma \phi_p + \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \left(\frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial T} \phi_p + \Gamma \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial T} \right) \right) \dots \\ &\dots - \frac{\text{tr} \mathbf{B}^n}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.17})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{B}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} &= 3k^2 \left[\left(\frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \frac{1}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} - \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \right) \Gamma \text{dev} \phi \otimes \frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \dots \right. \\ &\dots \left. + \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \left(\text{dev} \phi \otimes \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} + \Gamma \frac{\partial \text{dev} \phi}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \right) \right] \dots \\ &\dots - \frac{1}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \text{dev} \mathbf{B}^{n*} \otimes \frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} + \frac{3}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{B}^{n*}}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{Q}} \frac{\partial \text{dev} \phi}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.18})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{B}}{\partial T} &= 3k^2 \left(\left(\frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} \frac{1}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} - \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} \right) \Gamma \text{dev} \phi + \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \left(\text{dev} \phi \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial T} + \Gamma \frac{\partial \text{dev} \phi}{\partial T} \right) \right) \dots \\ &\dots - \frac{\text{dev} \mathbf{B}^{n*}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} + \frac{3}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{B}^{n*}}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{Q}} \frac{\partial \text{dev} \phi}{\partial T}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.19})$$

where $\frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma}$ is given in Eq. (E.7) and:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} &= -m_{\gamma_c} \left(\frac{1}{H_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial T} + \left(-\frac{1}{H_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} + \frac{1}{H_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma \partial T} \right) \Delta\gamma \right) \dots \\ &\dots - \frac{1}{H_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} - \left(-\frac{1}{H_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} \frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} + \frac{1}{H_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T^2} \right) \Delta T. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.20})$$

The derivatives of ϕ_p rearranged in terms of $\frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial(\cdot)}$ using Eqs. (G.16) and (G.17) :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} &= \left(1 + 2\beta\Gamma \left(\frac{\partial \hat{p}_e}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} + \frac{k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{3C_{\mathbf{B}}} \right) \right)^{-1} \left[\frac{\partial \hat{p}_e}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} \left(\mathbf{I} : \frac{1}{2} \mathcal{L}_e^{\text{pr}} - 2\beta\phi_p \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \right) \dots \right. \\ &\dots - \frac{2\beta k^2}{3} \left(\left(\frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \frac{1}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} - \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \right) \frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \Gamma \phi_p + \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \phi_p \right) \dots \\ &\dots \left. + \frac{1}{3} \frac{\text{tr} \mathbf{B}^n}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.21})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial T} &= \left(1 + 2\beta\Gamma \left(\frac{\partial \hat{p}_e}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} + \frac{k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{3C_{\mathbf{B}}} \right) \right)^{-1} \left[\frac{\partial \hat{p}_e^{aT}}{\partial T} - 2\beta\phi_p \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial T} \frac{\partial \hat{p}_e}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} \dots \right. \\ &\dots \left. - \frac{2\beta k^2}{3} \left(\left(\frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} \frac{1}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} - \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} \right) \Gamma \phi_p + \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial T} \phi_p \right) + \frac{1}{3} \frac{\text{tr} \mathbf{B}^n}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.22})$$

Similarly, the derivatives of $\text{dev} \phi$ rearranged in terms of $\frac{\partial \text{dev} \phi}{\partial(\cdot)}$ using Eqs. (G.18) and (G.19) as given below:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \text{dev} \phi}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} &= \left(\mathcal{I} + 3\Gamma \left(\frac{\partial \text{dev} \hat{\tau}_e}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} \otimes \mathbf{I} + \frac{\partial \text{dev} \hat{\tau}_e}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{E}_e} : \mathcal{I}^{\text{dev}} \right) : \mathcal{I} \dots \right. \\ &\dots \left. + \frac{3\Gamma k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} : \mathcal{I} + \frac{3}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{B}^{n*}}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{Q}} \right)^{-1} : \mathcal{D}_1, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.23})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \text{dev} \phi}{\partial T} &= \left(\mathcal{I} + 3\Gamma \left(\frac{\partial \text{dev} \hat{\tau}_e}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} \otimes \mathbf{I} + \frac{\partial \text{dev} \hat{\tau}_e}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{E}_e} : \mathcal{I}^{\text{dev}} \right) : \mathcal{I} \dots \right. \\ &\dots \left. + \frac{3\Gamma k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} : \mathcal{I} + \frac{3}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \frac{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{B}^{n*}}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{Q}} \right)^{-1} : \mathcal{D}_{1T}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.24})$$

where the 4th order \mathcal{D}_1 and the 2nd order \mathcal{D}_{1T} tensors are given below:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_1 &= \left(\frac{\partial \text{dev} \hat{\tau}_e}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} \otimes \mathbf{I} + \frac{\partial \text{dev} \hat{\tau}_e}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{E}_e} : \mathcal{I}^{\text{dev}} \right) : \left(\frac{1}{2} \mathcal{L}_e^{\text{pr}} - \left(\mathbf{Q} \otimes \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} + \frac{2\beta\Gamma}{3} \mathbf{I} \otimes \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \right) \right) \dots \\ &\dots - 3k^2 \left(\left(\frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \frac{1}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} - \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \right) \Gamma \text{dev} \phi \otimes \frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} + \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \text{dev} \phi \otimes \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \right) \dots \\ &\dots + \frac{1}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \text{dev} \mathbf{B}^{n*} \otimes \frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.25})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{1T} &= \frac{\partial \text{dev} \hat{\tau}_e^{aT}}{\partial T} - \left(\frac{\partial \text{dev} \hat{\tau}_e}{\partial \text{tr} \mathbf{E}_e} \otimes \mathbf{I} + \frac{\partial \text{dev} \hat{\tau}_e}{\partial \text{dev} \mathbf{E}_e} : \mathcal{I}^{\text{dev}} \right) : \left(\mathbf{Q} \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial T} + \frac{2\beta\Gamma}{3} \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial T} \mathbf{I} \right) \dots \\ &\dots - 3k^2 \left(\left(\frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} \frac{1}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} - \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} \right) \Gamma \text{dev} \phi + \frac{H_{\mathbf{B}}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}} \text{dev} \phi \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial T} \right) \dots \\ &\dots + \frac{\text{dev} \mathbf{B}^{n*}}{C_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial C_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.26})$$

where the derivatives $\frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}$ and $\frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial T}$ come respectively from Eq. (G.21) and Eq. (G.22). Lastly, the tensors $\frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}$, $\frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial T}$, $\frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}$ and $\frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial T}$ are derived from the consistency conditions of yielding in the following subsection. Note that, there is no distinction between $\frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial(\cdot)}$ and $\frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial(\cdot)}$.

Appendix G.2. Consistency Conditions of Plasticity

The consistency conditions imply that the extended yield surface follows the plastic driving stress state for plastic deformation to occur, i.e., $d\bar{F} = 0$, see Eq. (84). This essentially eliminates the change in the unknown variables, i.e., $d\Delta\gamma$ and $d\Gamma$, allowing the estimation of their partial derivatives with respect to the independent variables \mathbf{C}_e^{pr} and T . Therefore, $d\bar{F}(\mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}, T; \Delta\gamma, \Gamma) = 0$. This condition must remain true with respect to varying \mathbf{C}_e^{pr} and T for plastic deformation:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} + \frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} + \left[\frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial \Gamma} + \frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial \Gamma} \right] \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} = 0, \quad (\text{G.27})$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial T} + \frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial T} + \left[\frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial \Gamma} + \frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial \Delta\gamma} \frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial \Gamma} \right] \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial T} = 0, \quad (\text{G.28})$$

where the derivative $\frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial \Gamma}$ comes from the relation $G(\Delta\gamma, \Gamma)$ in Eq. (B.24):

$$\frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial \Gamma} = k \left(A + \Gamma \frac{\partial A}{\partial \Gamma} \right). \quad (\text{G.29})$$

The derivatives of \bar{F} with respect to \mathbf{C}_e^{pr} and T read:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} = a_2 \alpha \phi_e^{\alpha-1} \frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} - a_1 \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}, \quad (\text{G.30})$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial T} = H_{2T} \phi_e^\alpha + a_2 \alpha \phi_e^{\alpha-1} \frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial T} - H_{1T} \phi_p - a_1 \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial T} - H_{0T} - \left(\frac{\Gamma}{\Delta t} \frac{\partial \eta(T)}{\partial T} \right) p \left(\eta(T) \frac{\Gamma}{\Delta t} \right)^{p-1}, \quad (\text{G.31})$$

where, using Eq. (E.8),

$$\frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} = \frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\phi}} : \frac{\partial \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\phi}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{\text{dev } \boldsymbol{\phi}}{\phi_e} : \frac{\partial \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\phi}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}, \quad (\text{G.32})$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial T} = \frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\phi}} : \frac{\partial \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\phi}}{\partial T} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{\text{dev } \boldsymbol{\phi}}{\phi_e} : \frac{\partial \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\phi}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}, \quad (\text{G.33})$$

since $\frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\phi}} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{\text{dev } \boldsymbol{\phi}}{\phi_e}$. Using the Eqs. (82), the temperature derivatives of the hardening moduli read:

$$H_{2T} = -\frac{\alpha}{\sigma_c^{\alpha+1}} \frac{\partial \sigma_c}{\partial T} = -\frac{\alpha}{\sigma_c^\alpha} \frac{1}{a_{T_\gamma}^c} \frac{\partial a_{T_\gamma}^c}{\partial T}, \quad (\text{G.34})$$

$$H_{1T} = \frac{\partial a_1}{\partial T} = \frac{3}{\sigma_c} \left[\frac{\alpha m^{\alpha-1}}{m+1} - \frac{m^\alpha - 1}{(m+1)^2} \right] \frac{\partial m}{\partial T}, \quad (\text{G.35})$$

$$H_{0T} = \frac{\partial a_0}{\partial T} = \frac{(\alpha m^{\alpha-1} + 1)(m+1) - m^\alpha - m}{(m+1)^2} \frac{\partial m}{\partial T}, \quad (\text{G.36})$$

using,

$$\frac{\partial m}{\partial T} = \frac{1}{\sigma_c} \left(\frac{\sigma_t}{a_{T_\gamma}^t} \frac{\partial a_{T_\gamma}^t}{\partial T} - m \frac{\sigma_c}{a_{T_\gamma}^c} \frac{\partial a_{T_\gamma}^c}{\partial T} \right). \quad (\text{G.37})$$

The derivatives of $\Delta\gamma$ at constant Γ can be evaluated directly from its definition in Eq. (B.13):

$$\left. \frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \right|_\Gamma = k\Gamma \frac{\partial A}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \quad \text{and} \quad \left. \frac{\partial \Delta\gamma}{\partial T} \right|_\Gamma = k\Gamma \frac{\partial A}{\partial T}, \quad (\text{G.38})$$

where the derivatives of the scalar A read:

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} = \frac{1}{2A} \left(12\phi_e \frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} + \frac{8}{3} \beta^2 \phi_p \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial A}{\partial T} = \frac{1}{2A} \left(12\phi_e \frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial T} + \frac{8}{3} \beta^2 \phi_p \frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial T} \right), \quad (\text{G.39})$$

with the derivatives $\frac{\partial \phi_p}{\partial(\cdot)}$ and $\frac{\partial^{\text{dev}} \phi}{\partial(\cdot)}$ derived in Appendix G.1. The derivatives of Γ are obtained writing the consistency conditions, Eqs. (G.27) and (G.28), in terms of $\frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial(\cdot)}$:

$$\frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} = -\frac{\frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} + \frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial \Delta \gamma} \frac{\partial \Delta \gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}}{\frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial \Gamma} + \frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial \Delta \gamma} \frac{\partial \Delta \gamma}{\partial \Gamma}} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial T} = -\frac{\frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial T} + \frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial \Delta \gamma} \frac{\partial \Delta \gamma}{\partial T}}{\frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial \Gamma} + \frac{\partial \bar{F}}{\partial \Delta \gamma} \frac{\partial \Delta \gamma}{\partial \Gamma}}, \quad (\text{G.40})$$

and finally, using Eq. (G.29), the derivatives of γ are written as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} = k\Gamma \frac{\partial A}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} + k \left(A + \Gamma \frac{\partial A}{\partial \Gamma} \right) \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial T} = k\Gamma \frac{\partial A}{\partial T} + k \left(A + \Gamma \frac{\partial A}{\partial \Gamma} \right) \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial T}, \quad (\text{G.41})$$

where $\frac{\partial A}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}$ and $\frac{\partial A}{\partial T}$ come from Eq. (G.39).

Appendix G.3. Mullins's Effect and Free Energy Derivatives

The derivatives of the Mullins's state variable, $\zeta(\hat{\psi}, \hat{\psi}_{\max})$, are explicitly stated below:

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \hat{\psi}} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial T} = \frac{\partial \zeta_T}{\partial T} + \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \hat{\psi}} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}}{\partial T}, \quad (\text{G.42})$$

where, the derivative $\frac{\partial \zeta_T}{\partial T}$ is the dependance of the Mullins' parameter on temperature (elaborated below) and the derivatives of $\hat{\psi}_{\max}$ are null for non-null derivatives of ζ , i.e., as stated before the maximum free energy is constant in unloading/reloading during the evolution of Mullins's effect. The derivatives of ζ are straightforward using its definition in Eq. (24):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \hat{\psi}} &= \frac{z}{\hat{\psi}_{\max}} - \frac{z\hat{\psi}}{\hat{\psi}_{\max}^2} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max}}{\partial \hat{\psi}}, \\ \frac{\partial \zeta_T}{\partial T} &= -\frac{\partial z}{\partial T} \left(1 - \frac{\hat{\psi}}{\hat{\psi}_{\max}} \right) - \frac{z\hat{\psi}}{\hat{\psi}_{\max}^2} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max}}{\partial \hat{\psi}} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}}{\partial T}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.43})$$

where, the derivative $\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max}}{\partial \hat{\psi}}$ is as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max}}{\partial \hat{\psi}} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \zeta = 1, \\ 0, & \text{if } \zeta < 1, \end{cases} \quad (\text{G.44})$$

which ensures that the tangents of ζ remain zero in loading. Then, the derivatives of the free energy using Eq. (15), then Eq. (58) for $\hat{\psi}_{ve}$, are:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = \underbrace{\left(\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\infty}}{\partial \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}} + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_i}{\partial \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}} \right)}_{\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{ve}}{\partial \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}}} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} + \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{vp}}{\partial \mathbf{F}}, \quad (\text{G.45})$$

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}}{\partial T} = \underbrace{\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\infty}}{\partial T} + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_i}{\partial T}}_{\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{ve}}{\partial T}} + \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{ve}}{\partial \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}}{\partial T} + \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{vp}}{\partial T}, \quad (\text{G.46})$$

where, $\frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}$, $\frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}}{\partial T}$ and $\frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}}$ are given in Eqs. (G.7) and (G.8), respectively.

Furthermore, $\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\infty}}{\partial \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}}$ is different from $\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_{\infty} = \hat{p}_{\infty} \mathbf{I} + \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_{\infty}$ because of the regularisation function, as explained before in Section 3.5, and is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\infty}}{\partial \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}} &= \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_{\infty} + \frac{\partial f_{\text{reg}}}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}} \left(K_{\infty 0} \int_0^{\text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}} (A_t - C_{0\infty} A_c) \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}} d(\text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}) \right) \mathbf{I} \dots \\ &\dots + \frac{\partial f_{\text{reg}}}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}} \left(2G_{\infty 0} \int_0^{\text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e} (B_t - C_{0\infty} B_c) \text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e : d(\text{dev } \mathbf{E}_e) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.47})$$

and, $\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_i}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e}$ is different from $\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_i = \hat{p}_i \mathbf{I} + \text{dev } \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_i$, again because of the regularisation function and also the convolution integral solution which is an approximation to the viscoelastic ODEs shown before in Section 3.2. It is given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_i}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} &= \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_i \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} + \frac{\partial f_{\text{reg}}}{\partial \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i} \left(K_{i0} \int_0^{\text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i} (A_{ti} - C_{0i} A_{ci}) \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i d(\text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i) \right) \frac{\partial \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e} \dots \\ &\dots + \frac{\partial f_{\text{reg}}}{\partial \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i} \left(2G_{i0} \int_0^{\text{dev } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i} (B_{ti} - C_{0i} B_{ci}) \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i : d(\text{dev } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i) \right) \frac{\partial \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.48})$$

where the derivative $\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial \mathbf{E}_e}$ is given in the Appendix F.3. Then, $\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\infty}}{\partial T}$ is due to thermal expansion and reads:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\infty}}{\partial T} = -3 \left(\alpha_{\infty} + \frac{\partial \alpha_{\infty}}{\partial T} (T - T_0) \right) \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\infty}}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}}, \quad (\text{G.49})$$

where $\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\infty}}{\partial \text{tr } \mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}}$ is the volumetric part of the Eq. (G.47). Then, $\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_i}{\partial T}$, which is due to thermal expansion as well as the temperature dependency of the shift factor in the strain of a Maxwell branch, using Eq. (A.2), becomes:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_i}{\partial T} = \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_i}{\partial \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i} \frac{\partial \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial T} + 2G_{i0} \left(B_i \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i : \frac{\partial \text{dev } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}{\partial T} \right), \quad (\text{G.50})$$

where, the derivative $\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_i}{\partial \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i}$ is the volumetric part of Eq. (G.48) and the temperature derivatives of $\boldsymbol{\mathfrak{E}}_i$ are given in Eqs. (F.25). The terms $\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{vp}}{\partial \mathbf{F}}$ and $\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{vp}}{\partial T}$, using Eq. (75), are shown below:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{vp}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} &= \frac{1}{k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}} \left(\mathbf{B} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \right) - \frac{\mathbf{B} : \mathbf{B}}{2k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \gamma} \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \mathbf{F}} + a_{T\gamma}{}^c R_a \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}}, \\ \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{vp}}{\partial T} &= \frac{1}{k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}} \left(\mathbf{B} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial T} \right) - \frac{\mathbf{B} : \mathbf{B}}{2k^2 H_{\mathbf{B}}^2} \left(\frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial T} + \frac{\partial H_{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial \gamma} \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial T} \right) \dots \\ &\dots + a_{T\gamma}{}^c R_a \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial T} + \frac{\partial a_{T\gamma}{}^c}{\partial T} \int_0^{\gamma} R_a d\gamma, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.51})$$

where $R_a = R/a_{T\gamma}{}^c$ is written for convenience following the definition of the isotropic hardening force R in Eq. (87), the derivatives of the backstress \mathbf{B} are given in Eqs. (G.16-G.19) and the derivatives of the equivalent plastic strain γ are given in Eqs. (G.41).

Appendix G.4. Heat Flux Derivatives

Thermal conductivity is taken as a scalar (χ) which is in line with the assumption of isotropy. The derivatives of the thermal flux in the reference configuration using Eq. (14) are estimated as:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial T} = \frac{1}{\chi} \mathbf{Q} \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial T}, \quad (\text{G.52})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial \mathbf{H}} = -J \chi \mathbf{C}^{-1}, \quad (\text{G.53})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = \frac{\mathbf{Q}}{J} \otimes \frac{\partial J}{\partial \mathbf{F}} - J \chi \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}^{-1}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \cdot \mathbf{H}, \quad (\text{G.54})$$

where $J = \det \mathbf{F}$ is the Jacobian of the deformation, \otimes in the last equation is intended in a manner to produce a 3rd order tensor and the following derivatives are used:

$$\frac{\partial J}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = J \mathbf{F}^{-T}, \quad (\text{G.55})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{C}^{-1}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = -\mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1}. \quad (\text{G.56})$$

Appendix G.5. Mechanical Source Derivatives

The mechanical heat source, in Eq. (90) is differentiated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial W_M}{\partial \mathbf{F}} &= \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \left(-C_p \dot{T} + \boldsymbol{\phi} : \mathbf{D}_p - R \dot{\gamma} \right) + \zeta \left(\left(\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\phi}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \right)^{1,2} : \mathbf{D}_p + \boldsymbol{\phi} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}_p}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \right) \dots \\ &\dots + \zeta \left(-\frac{\partial R}{\partial \gamma} \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \dot{\gamma} - \frac{R}{\Delta t} \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \right) - \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max} \partial \mathbf{F}} \dot{\hat{\psi}}_{\max} - \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max}} \frac{1}{\Delta t} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max}}{\partial \mathbf{F}}, \\ \frac{\partial W_M}{\partial T} &= \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial T} \left(-C_p \dot{T} + \boldsymbol{\phi} : \mathbf{D}_p - R \dot{\gamma} \right) + \zeta \left(-\frac{C_p}{\Delta t} + \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\phi}}{\partial T} : \mathbf{D}_p + \boldsymbol{\phi} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}_p}{\partial T} \right) \dots \\ &\dots + \zeta \left(-\left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial T} + \frac{\partial R}{\partial \gamma} \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial T} \right) \dot{\gamma} - \frac{R}{\Delta t} \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial T} \right) - \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max} \partial T} \dot{\hat{\psi}}_{\max} - \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max}} \frac{1}{\Delta t} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max}}{\partial T}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.57})$$

where the derivatives of $\boldsymbol{\phi}$ are given in Eqs. (G.21-G.24); the conversion tensor, $\frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}}$, is given in Eq. (G.8) and the derivatives of the equivalent plastic strain γ are given in Eqs. (G.41). As to the derivatives of the rate of plastic deformation $\mathbf{D}_p = \frac{\Gamma \mathbf{Q}}{\Delta t}$:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{D}_p}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = \frac{1}{\Delta t} \frac{\partial (\Gamma \mathbf{Q})}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}} : \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}_e^{\text{pr}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}_p}{\partial T} = \frac{1}{\Delta t} \frac{\partial (\Gamma \mathbf{Q})}{\partial T}, \quad (\text{G.58})$$

where the derivatives of the corrector tensor $\Gamma \mathbf{Q}$ are given in Eqs. (G.7). The derivatives of the isotropic hardening force R stemming from its definition in Eq. (87) are as follows:

$$\frac{\partial R}{\partial \gamma} = a_{T\gamma} c H_c \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial R}{\partial T} = \frac{\partial a_{T\gamma} c}{\partial T} R_a. \quad (\text{G.59})$$

Lastly, the derivatives with respect to the maximum free energy, $\hat{\psi}_{\max}$, are obtained from the definition of ζ in Eq. (24):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max} \partial \mathbf{F}} &= \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max} \partial \hat{\psi}} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = \left(\frac{-z \hat{\psi}}{\hat{\psi}_{\max}^2} + \frac{z \hat{\psi}^2}{\hat{\psi}_{\max}^3} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max}}{\partial \hat{\psi}} \right) \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}}{\partial \mathbf{F}}, \\ \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max} \partial T} &= -\frac{\partial z}{\partial T} \frac{\hat{\psi}^2}{2 \hat{\psi}_{\max}^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max} \partial \hat{\psi}} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}}{\partial T} = -\frac{\partial z}{\partial T} \frac{\hat{\psi}^2}{2 \hat{\psi}_{\max}^2} + \left(\frac{-z \hat{\psi}}{\hat{\psi}_{\max}^2} + \frac{z \hat{\psi}^2}{\hat{\psi}_{\max}^3} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max}}{\partial \hat{\psi}} \right) \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}}{\partial T}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.60})$$

and the derivatives of the maximum free energy:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} = \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max}}{\partial \hat{\psi}} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max}}{\partial T} = \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max}}{\partial \hat{\psi}} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}}{\partial T}, \quad (\text{G.61})$$

where the derivative $\frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_{\max}}{\partial \hat{\psi}}$ is given in Eq. (G.44) and serves the same purpose as to negate the corresponding terms in loading.